

Taigu School

also known as “Taigu Sect”, “Taigu Teaching”, “New Taizhou School”, “Yellow Cliff Teaching”, “Kongtong Teaching”, “Daxue Teaching”, “Dacheng Teaching”

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Entry tags: Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Daoist Traditions, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Religious Group, Chinese Religion, Chinese Folk Religions, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

The “Taigu School” 太谷學派 (and its various alternative names, such as “Taigu Teaching” 太谷教, “Yellow Cliff Teaching” 黃崖教, “Kongtong Teaching” 崆峒教, “Great Learning Teaching” 大學教, “Great Achievement Teaching” 大成教, etc.) refers to an esoteric genealogy of teaching in China spanning from the eighteenth century to the mid-twentieth century. The founding patriarch, Zhou Taigu 周太谷 (c. 1762–c. 1832, aka Zhou Gu 周穀, Zhou Xingyuan 周星垣, Kongtongzi 空同子/崆峒子, etc.), was from the Anhui province but mainly preached in Yangzhou of the Jiangnan region. The documentation of him is rare and often vague, but his followers believed he was the fifth “Sage” (following the several ancient “Sage-Kings” and Confucius) who had inherited the true “Way,” and it was reported (probably distortedly) that he had mastered various forms of occult arts, including divination, cure, talismans, incantations, exorcism, invisibility, and the sexual cultivation. Among his many followers, Zhang Jizhong 張積中 (c. 1805–1866, aka Zhang Shiqin 張石琴, Qi xiansheng 七先生, among many other aliases) brought his teaching to the north. In 1856, Zhang settled his family at Yellow Cliff 黃崖山, a remote mountain in Shandong province. More and more people and households joined him, and gradually a semi-independent community took shape. The community did have religious features, but it was by and large based on mutual aid and self-defense in order to keep safely away from the various rebel militia in that time. Nonetheless, it was accused as an “evil cult” and sanguinary oppressed by the local government in 1866, an incident that is usually known as the “Yellow Cliff Massacre.” Zhang’s cousin and fellow disciple, Li Guangxin 李光炘 (1808–1885, aka Li Qingfeng 李晴峰, Li Pingshan 李平山 and Longchuan xiansheng 龍川先生, among many other aliases), preached in the Jiangnan region and accumulated numerous followers, mostly men of letters, including many contemporary celebrities, such as the politician Mao Qingfan 毛慶藩 (1849–1927) and the novelist Liu E 劉鶚 (1857–1909). Starting from 1902, the teaching was based in the Guiqun Academy 歸群草堂 in Suzhou and was led by Li’s disciple Huang Baonian 黃葆年 (1845–1924, aka Huang Xipeng 黃隰朋 and Huang Guiqun 黃歸群), which was commonly known as the “Huang School 黃門” until it gradually declined and finally dissolved in the mid-twentieth century. The teaching defies a rash generalization. Extant analects of Zhou Taigu are mostly his idiosyncratic exegesis on the Confucian classic *The Book of Change* 易經, which has a syncretic inclination, integrating the Confucian, Buddhist, Daoist thoughts and even Millennialism beliefs. Biographical accounts of Zhou Taigu are also full of miracles, which resemble what are often seen in what we now call “popular religions” or “folk religions.” This tendency toward mysticism is observable in both Zhang Jizhong’s Yellow Cliff community and Li Guangxin’s master-disciple lineage. However, Huang Baonian, who was already a prominent Confucian scholar before leading the Guiqun Academy, made clear efforts of eliminating the occult elements from the teaching and establishing its Confucian legitimacy.

Date Range: 1762 CE - 1950 CE

Region: Shandong and Jiangnan

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China, Shandong, Jiangnan

The Shandong province and the lower Yangtze area that is usually called “Jiangnan,” including today’s Shanghai, southern Jiangsu province, northern

Zhejiang province, and parts of Anhui and Jiangxi provinces.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Membership/Group Interactions

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Scripture

Architecture, Geography

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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